

The Effect of Pulsed Laser on the Surface State of 3D-Printed Triply Periodic Structures in TiAl6V4 Alloy

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Abstract

In this study, the effect of laser treatment on the surface state of 3D-printed TiAl6V4 alloy with triply periodic structures was investigated. As-printed and chemically etched samples were used as reference materials to demonstrate surface changes and to illustrate the improvement in surface condition. Microscopic observations of the laser-treated sample confirmed morphological changes caused by the remelting of the initial surface, accompanied by the formation of wave-like structures during the process. The rapid cooling rate led to the formation of cracks that extended through the entire depth of the newly formed layer. Chemical and phase analyses revealed the predominant presence of Ti_xO_y ($x = 1-2$; $y = 1-3$) compounds, with observed differences between the as-printed and treated samples. Both surface modification approaches successfully removed un-sintered powder particles; however, laser processing did not thin the struts and walls, which positively affected mechanical properties. The best mechanical properties were found in the untreated samples, but laser-treated samples showed only a minimal reduction. For example, an untreated diamond-structured sample exhibited a yield strength of 93 ± 2 MPa, whereas a laser-treated sample showed a yield strength of 89 ± 3 MPa. Furthermore, the hardness of treated surface increased approximately by 60 % in comparison to as-printed state. Samples with a gyroid structure demonstrated significantly increased yield strength, compressive strength, and ductility compared to those with a diamond structure. Corrosion resistance testing did not reveal the occurrence of localized corrosion, indicating that laser surface treatment did not negatively impact the corrosion resistance of TiAlV alloys. The relative metabolic activity on laser-treated materials exceeded the 70% normative limit relative to the metabolic activity of control cells. Thus, all the tested materials can be considered cytocompatible, and therefore the laser treatment is promising for Ti-based personalized 3D implants.

Keywords: Triply periodic structures; Ti-6Al-4V; Surface treatment; Pulse laser; Characterization

1. Introduction

Titanium and its alloys belong among the most important engineering materials used in various applications. They are particularly attractive for highly demanding applications in the aerospace industry and in medicine, thanks to their exceptional and well-balanced properties, including high specific strength (strength to weight ratio), corrosion resistance, or good biocompatibility [1, 2]. Within the category of metallic materials for biomedical applications, pure titanium (α phase) demonstrates the highest biocompatibility. However, its relatively low mechanical properties preclude its use in load-bearing components, such as hip, knee, or spinal implants, in its unalloyed form. Nevertheless, commercial pure titanium could be still used for skull implants or bone plates because pure titanium is free from toxic alloying elements and exhibits higher ductility than alloys [3]. To enhance its mechanical performance, titanium is often alloyed to create materials with superior strength, albeit at the expense of reduced biocompatibility. The Ti-6Al-4V alloy is indeed one of the most commonly studied metallic materials for biomedical industry, primarily due to its relatively low density, high strength, and good corrosion resistance [4]. The microstructure of Ti-6Al-4V alloy contains mixture of α and β phase with α phase being dominant [5, 6]. The presence of α phase results in e. g. poor wear properties [5]. Another drawback is also the possible toxic effect of Al and V for the body tissues [3]. Despite the mentioned disadvantages, the Ti-6Al-4V alloy remains the most used and studied alloy for implants.

61 Stress shielding effect is one of the primary obstacles hindering the seamless use of these materials in
62 implantology. This effect is caused by the mismatch in Young's modulus between the implant and the bone leading to the
63 implant failure [3, 7]. The issue of stress shielding can be mitigated by introducing a porous structure into the materials.
64 A porous structure can be achieved through various methods, such as using powder metallurgy, where a pore-forming
65 agent is added to the powder mixture [7-9], or through 3D printing and foaming technologies [8, 9]. Furthermore,
66 materials with a porous structure enhance osseointegration by promoting the ingrowth of bone tissue into the implants [3,
67 9, 10]. Porosity thus significantly enhances the integration between the implant and the bone because porous materials
68 contain opened or closed voids in the structure resulting in the spaces between them [9]. The pore size is crucial for
69 effective cell adhesion to the implant. The shape of the pores also plays an important role; for instance, pores with a cubic
70 cross-section achieve better cell adhesion than those with a spherical cross-section [9, 11]. Additionally, different tissues
71 have varying requirements for implants, which can sometimes conflict with each other. There is no universal consensus
72 on the ideal porosity, pore size, or their interconnectivity. In designing these porous structures, two main approaches are
73 used: regular and irregular structures.

74 As was mentioned above, the porous titanium and titanium alloys could be produced using powder metallurgy
75 or additive technology. Powder metallurgy is a relatively simple and efficient method for fabricating porous implants.
76 Compared to alternative manufacturing techniques, it is more cost-effective and reduces material waste to a minimum.
77 Moreover, powder metallurgy enables the production of intricate porous structures [9]. On the other hand, the production
78 of porous structures through 3D printing is based on CAD models. This approach achieves high precision and allows for
79 the precise customization of the elemental unit. As a result, it is possible to obtain highly complex yet accurate products.
80 These 3D-printed porous structures are applicable in medicine for the manufacture of patient-specific implants [6, 9].
81 Additive manufacturing technologies, commonly known as 3D printing, for titanium implants can be categorized into
82 two groups: powder bed fusion (PBF) and directed energy deposition (DED) [3, 6, 12, 13]. Powder bed fusion is further
83 subdivided into laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF), referred to as selective laser melting (SLM), and electron beam powder
84 bed fusion (E-PBF). SLM, aimed at reducing the elastic modulus while preserving biomechanical properties through the
85 incorporation of micropores, is the most widely used method for manufacturing titanium implants [6, 14, 15]. In SLM, a
86 focused laser beam selectively scans and melts a defined layer of the powder bed, causing the powder particles to fuse
87 according to the CAD data of the specified slice geometry [6, 16]. The main drawback is the presence of surface defects
88 and residual stresses [2, 13, 17, 18], which can lead to issues with the subsequent biological response (osteoblastic cell
89 adhesion, growth, or differentiation) [19]. The interactions between biomaterials and tissue, as well as the process of bone
90 healing, are significantly influenced by the chemical composition and surface topography of the implanted material. SLM
91 often results in final products that require post-processing surface treatments, as partially melted particles typically remain
92 on the surface following the printing stage [13]. These particles pose the risk of being released and potentially circulating
93 within the human body [20]. Un-melted particles can be effectively removed by sandblasting or etching, which has been
94 shown to have additional beneficial effects. For instance, surfaces that are roughened through sandblasting and acid-
95 etching have been shown to promote bone cell proliferation and enhance the secretion of extracellular matrix, thereby
96 supporting bone regeneration [3, 21]. The presence of partially melted particles on the surface can be removed through
97 double acid etching [20]. In addition to the previously mentioned sandblasting and acid etching, the surface can also be
98 modified using a plasma spraying, hot isostatic pressing (HIP), vibratory finishing, or laser polishing [6, 13, 16, 22, 23].
99 A sandblasted and acid-etched surface is considered one of the most effective modifications for commercially pure
100 titanium, featuring a moderately rough topography that promotes strong interaction with bone tissue. This surface
101 structure has been widely accepted for its ability to enhance osseointegration and improve the overall performance of
102 titanium implants, despite the fact that the process negatively impacts corrosion resistance due to slight surface changes
103 [21, 24].

104 There are numerous publications dedicated to the modification of the surface of 3D-printed products, with
105 particular focus on chemical etching [24-31]. In work [25] was shown that a mixture of HF and HNO₃ is more effective
106 for uniform etching compared to the use of HF alone. Acid etching should be also performed after sandblasting, as the
107 sandblasting process induces the formation of microcracks, which are not readily apparent despite the surface appearing
108 smooth [26]. Moreover, acid etching increases internal porosity, while the thickness of the struts decreases, resulting in a
109 reduction of mechanical properties [28]. Study [27], on the other hand, demonstrated the differences between three distinct
110 surface modification techniques: chemical polishing, electropolishing, blasting, a combination of electropolishing and
111 blasting, and finally, laser polishing. In all cases, the surface roughness was greater when laser polishing was applied. In
112 addition, a laser beam can be focused onto a metallic surface to perform a wide range of treatments, including remelting,
113 alloying, and cladding, which are employed to enhance the wear and corrosion resistance of titanium alloys [23, 32, 33].
114 Based on the existing publications, laser-based surface modification appears to be the most effective method; however,
115 the majority of research focuses primarily on chemical etching, and thus far, laser technology has only been applied to
116 compact materials, not porous ones. Turning and milling were also investigated and both operations significantly reduced
117 surface roughness [34].

118 The customization of surface texture, along with the post-processing optimization and modification of surfaces,
119 represents the future direction in the development of 3D-printed biomaterials. This study aims to characterize samples
120 with triply periodic structures whose surface was influenced by laser treatment, which was used for the first time on
121 porous alloys. Compared to chemical etching, laser processing offers the advantage of particle removal and melting
122 followed by rapid cooling, leading to surface refinement, and hardening. The surface of the samples was analyzed using
123 advanced techniques such as X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy. Furthermore, the
124 morphology, structure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance were investigated, along with essential
125 cytotoxicity tests for biomaterials.

126

127 2. Experimental

128 2.1 Preparation of samples and surface treatment

129 Atomized powder of the TiAl6V4 (wt. %) alloy was used for the preparation of TiAl6V4 scaffolds with triply
130 periodic minimal surface structures using the SLM method. The alloy powder was prepared by a gas atomization process
131 under a protective Ar atmosphere. The particle size distribution of atomized powders was determined by laser diffraction
132 analysis using SYNC particle analyzer (Microtrac Retsch GmbH) combining laser diffraction with dynamic image.
133 Measurement was performed by the wet (dispersion medium - isopropanol) and dry method. The particle size distribution
134 was characterized by d-values (d_{10} , d_{50} , and d_{90}) which are the intercepts for 10%, 50% and 90% of the mass frequency
135 distribution. The particles had a spherical shape with $d_{10} = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{50} = 32.9 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{90} = 48.1 \mu\text{m}$. The SLM process was
136 performed using an M2 Cusing printer, with the process parameters set as follows: laser power of 200 W, scanning spacing
137 of $30 \mu\text{m}$, and scanning speed of $800 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The process was performed under Ar protective atmosphere. Samples were
138 manufactured with diamond or gyroid structures and a unit size of 1.35 and 2 mm, respectively (Fig. 1).

139 **Fig. 1:** The structure of a) diamond and b) gyroid unit cells; c) macrostructure of the 3D-printed gyroid sample,
140 with an arrow indicating the build direction
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143 As-printed materials with diamond (D) and gyroid (G) structures were processed by laser treatment (L) and
144 chemical etching (E) to remove adhered spherical powder particles from the surface of the scaffold and decrease the
145 overall roughness of the last layer. For the laser treatment (DL, GL), an excimer laser, Coherent Leap 100K, was used in
146 pulse mode with a frequency of 1 Hz. Each sample was treated with 50 pulses and an energy of $3 \text{ J}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Exposed area
147 of the sample in one step was $5 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$, i.e. 15 mm^2 , and the large area exposure was achieved by step motor with sample
148 movement in air. Chemical etching (DE, GE) was performed in a solution with the following composition: 20 mL HF,
149 200 mL HNO_3 , and 780 mL H_2O . The composition of the etching bath was adopted from Fojt et al. [35]. The process was
150 carried out in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min with 30 mL of the etching solution at ambient temperature. After etching, the
151 samples were cleaned with distilled water and ethanol in the ultrasonic bath to effectively clean the entire sample. The
152 etched samples were also remeasured and weighed after the process to evaluate the dimensional changes caused by the
153 treatment.

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155 2.2 Surface characterization and microstructure

156 The morphology of the samples was examined using a JEOL JSM-IT500HR scanning electron microscope. Laser
157 scanning confocal microscopy (LSCM) was employed to measure surface roughness and generate height/laser intensity
158 maps using an Olympus LEXT OLS5000, equipped with a 50x long working distance objective.

159 X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were conducted using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro powder diffractometer
160 with a cobalt anode ($\lambda = 1.789 \text{ \AA}$). The measurements utilized the Bragg-Brentano geometry with a 1° divergence slit,
161 0.02 rad Soller slits, a β -filter, and a linear detector. Data processing was performed using the Rietveld refinement method
162 within the TOPAS software.

163 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed using an AXIS Supra device with an emission current
164 of 10 mA . For each sample, two separate measurements were taken. The resulting spectra were analyzed and fitted using
165 CasaXPS software.

166 The Raman spectra were measured using a Raman dispersive spectrometer from Thermo Scientific, model DXR
167 Microscope, which is equipped with an Olympus confocal microscope. A 532 nm wavelength laser with an input power
168 of 10 mW was used as the excitation source. A 900 grooves per mm grating was applied. The detector was a multichannel
169 thermoelectrically cooled CCD camera. Samples were measured at $50x$ magnification with a measuring spot size of
170 approximately $1 \mu\text{m}^2$. Measurements were conducted with a power of 9 mW , a measurement time of 10 s , and with 10
171 accumulations of the spectrum. The Omnic 9 software (Thermo Scientific) was used for spectrum processing. Four spectra
172 were measured for every sample.

173 The microstructure and the number of adhered particles were observed using a Nikon Eclipse MA200
174 metallographic microscope and a Tescan Mira II scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive
175 spectrometer (EDS). Samples for microstructural observations in the normal direction were embedded in EpoxyCure™
176 2 resin and ground using P80–P2500 sandpapers. Subsequently, the samples were polished using D2 diamond paste (2--
177 $3 \mu\text{m}$) and etched with Kroll's reagent (5 mL HNO_3 , 10 mL HF , $85 \text{ mL H}_2\text{O}$).

178 2.3 Mechanical properties

180 Compressive tests were performed using cylindrical samples with a diameter of 14 mm , a height of 6 mm , and a
181 loading speed of $0.035 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ at ambient temperature. A LabTest 5.250SP1-VM universal testing machine was used for
182 testing. Nanoindentation tests were performed to determine hardness (H_{IT}) and indentation elastic modulus (E_{IT}) of surface
183 area affected by laser and bulk material using NHT² nanoindentation tester equipped with Berkovich diamond tip.
184 Maximum applied load was 2 mN , loading cycle consisted of 10 s loading, 5 s hold at maximum load, and 10 s unloading.
185 Measured load-depth data were evaluated using Oliver-Pharr method [36] according to standard ISO 14577. At least 8
186 valid measurements were performed and statistically processed in every investigated area.

187 2.4 Corrosion tests

189 Before measurement or surface treatment, every sample was degreased for 5 min in an ultrasonic bath in a
190 detergent solution, followed by 5 min in ethanol.

191 The susceptibility to non-uniform corrosion was measured according to the ASTM F2129 standard in phosphate-
192 buffered saline (PBS) (see **Table 1**) using a three-electrode setup with a reference Ag/AgCl electrode ($3 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \text{ KCl}$,
193 abbreviated as SSCE). Due to the high real surface area of the working electrode, a platinum mesh counter electrode was
194 used during the measurement. Before starting the measurement, dissolved oxygen was removed by bubbling the
195 electrolyte with nitrogen gas for at least 30 min . After stabilizing the open circuit potential (OCP) for 1 h , the polarization
196 scan rate was set to $1 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, and the samples were polarized to 0.83 V/SSCE . Once the potential reached 0.83 V/SSCE ,
197 the scan rate was reversed until the potential returned to the initial values, at which point the experiment was terminated.
198 Due to the unknown real surface area, a geometrical area of 1.77 cm^2 was chosen for all measured samples, which were
199 in compact form.

200 **Table 1:** Composition of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS)

Chemical reagent	Concentration ($\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$)
NaCl	8
KCl	0.2
Na ₂ HPO ₄	1.15
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.2

202 For longer-term exposure, a physiological saline solution containing $9 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \text{ NaCl}$ (FS) was chosen due to its
203 higher Cl^- concentration and lack of possible precipitates that could form on the sample surface. The electrode setup
204 included a reference SSCE electrode with a tip filled with agar gel along with two glassy-carbon counter electrodes.
205 During exposure, the OCP and polarization resistance ($\pm 20 \text{ mV/OCP}$, $0.125 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) of each sample were monitored to
206 detect any electrochemical changes occurring on the surface. To assess susceptibility to localised corrosion after exposure,
207 a cyclic polarization scan (CP) was performed at a rate of $1 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ with a potential scan reversal at 0.83 V/SSCE .

208 2. 5 Test on extracts (ISO 10993-5)

209 Samples were cleaned by sonication in EtOH (96%, 15 min) and distilled water (15 min) and then sterilized by
210 autoclaving (121 °C, 20 min). Replicates of Ti-Al-V material with surface modification (TiAl6V4 - laser) and raw Ti-Al-
211 V material (TiAl6V4 - as printed) were immersed in the test media – MEM (minimal essential media, Sigma-Aldrich,
212 cat. no. M0446) with 5% foetal bovine serum (FBS) or DMEM/F-12 Ham's (Sigma-Aldrich, cat. no. D6434) with 5%
213 FBS and 2.5 mmol · L⁻¹ Alanine-glutamine. The immersed materials were then incubated in tubes at 37 °C with constant
214 shaking (100 rpm) for 24 h. The S/V ratio was 1.25 cm² · mL⁻¹.

215 Cell lines of mouse fibroblasts (L929, recommended by the ISO 10993-5) and human foetal osteoblasts (hFOB
216 1.19) were trypsinized, resuspended in appropriate culture medium (L929: MEM with 10% FBS or hFOB 1.19: DMEM/F-
217 12 Ham's with 10% FBS and 2.5 mmol · L⁻¹ Alanine-glutamine), and diluted to a concentration of 1 · 10⁵ cells · mL⁻¹ (L929)
218 or 2 · 10⁵ cells · mL⁻¹ (hFOB 1.19). These cell suspensions were then pipetted (100 µL) into the wells of a 96-well plate
219 and incubated for 24 h in the CO₂ incubator under standard conditions. The next day, media were aspirated from the 96-
220 well plates, and 100 µL of extracts from the samples were pipetted onto the cells. Control cells received 100 µL of the
221 test media alone. A positive control for cytotoxicity was prepared with test media containing 0.2% Tween. The cells were
222 then placed in a CO₂ incubator for another 24 h under standard conditions. On the third day, the metabolic activity of the
223 cells was measured using resazurin solutions [37]. The wells in the plates were emptied and the cells were gently washed
224 with 100 µL of sterile phosphate buffer. Then, 100 µL of a solution of resazurin (25 µg · mL⁻¹ in culture media without
225 phenol red) was pipetted to the cells. The cells were incubated for ~2 h in the CO₂ incubator until the colour of the media
226 went from blue to purple. Fluorescence of resorufin was then measured with a Fluoroskan Ascent FL (Ascent Software).
227 The excitation wavelength was 544 nm, and the emission wavelength was 590 nm. Cytotoxicity of the extracts was
228 evaluated as the relative metabolic activity of the cells compared to control cells. Extracts that reduced metabolic activity
229 below 70% of the control cells' activity were considered cytotoxic. Statistical evaluation was performed using GraphPad
230 Prism 7.0. The statistical significance of differences was determined by ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple
231 comparison test.

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233 2. 6 Direct contact test (quantitative)

234 Samples were transferred to 48-well plates (modified surface facing upwards). hFOB 1.19 cells were trypsinized,
235 resuspended in culture media, and diluted to a concentration of 2 · 10⁵ cells/mL. This cell suspension was pipetted onto
236 the samples. The 48-well plates were then placed in the CO₂ incubator under standard conditions. The metabolic activity
237 of the cells was measured at three time points of cultivation – after 24 h, 72 h, and 6 days, using resazurin [38] as described
238 above. Statistical evaluation of the metabolic activity of the cells on TiAl6V4 - as printed and TiAl6V4 - laser was
239 performed using GraphPad Prism 7.0. The statistical significance of differences was determined by ANOVA followed by
240 Tukey's multiple comparison test.

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242 2. 7 Qualitative cytocompatibility evaluation by SEM

243 hFOB 1.19 cells were trypsinized, resuspended in culture media and diluted so that 24,000 cells · cm² were
244 seeded onto the TiAl6V4 - as printed and TiAl6V4 - laser samples in the 48-well plates. The plates were then placed in
245 the CO₂ incubator under standard conditions. At three time points (24 h, 72 h, and 6 days, consistent with the evaluation
246 of the contact tests), media were aspirated from the wells, and the samples with cells were transferred to clean wells,
247 washed twice with sterile phosphate buffer, and cell fixation was performed [39]. Cells were fixed using Karnovsky's
248 solution for 1.5 h at ambient temperature. The samples were then transferred to clean wells and washed twice with 0.1M
249 cacodylate buffer. Cells fixed on the samples were dehydrated through a 10-min incubation in increasing concentrations
250 of EtOH (50%, 70%, 90%), followed by a wash in 99.8% EtOH and final incubation in 99.8% EtOH for 5 min. The
251 samples with cells were then dried using CPD with CO₂ and acetone. Finally, the samples with cells were coated with 10
252 nm of gold.

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255 **3. Results**

256 **3.1 Morphology**

257 Images of the surfaces of diamond and gyroid samples in their as-built state are shown in **Fig. 2**. The arrangement
258 of struts and walls in diamond and gyroid structures plays a significant role under loading conditions. The gyroid structure
259 is known for its smooth, continuous geometry, free from sharp edges or transitions [40]. This seamless continuity ensures
260 a more uniform distribution of mechanical stresses and can be advantageous in applications where tensile and compressive
261 strength are critical [41]. Additionally, it reduces stress concentration points, thereby extending the lifespan of
262 components. The diamond structure, on the other hand, consists of individual struts and nodes, resulting in sharp
263 transitions between parts of the structure. These sharp edges can be prone to stress accumulation, which may lead to
264 structural failure at these points under high loading conditions. The print quality can be assessed based on surface
265 morphology, which is influenced by residual un-melted metallic powder. These powder residues are particularly visible

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in the detailed images shown in **Fig. 2**. The images suggest that the samples were similar in terms of surface quality and morphology.

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Fig. 2: SEM images of a) diamond and b) gyroid structures with details of the surface morphologies

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Processed samples

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The surface of etched and laser-treated sample could be observed in **Fig. 3**. In the case of DE sample, a significant reduction in the presence of surface particles can be observed, as shown in **Fig. 3 a**. The sample treated with chemical etching shows a notable reduction in the thickness of the struts / walls forming the structure (**Fig. 3 a, 3 b**), which subsequently affects its mechanical properties negatively (see **Fig. 9**). Additionally, the composition of the etchant can influence the chemical composition of the surface, such as the presence of fluorides. Surface analysis using EDS revealed an increased fluorine content of around 1 wt. %. Moreover, nano-submicropores could be observed on the surface (**Fig. 3 a**). On the other hand, the surface was smoother after etching. The application of etching is also associated with mass loss due to the removal of un-melted particles [25]. When comparing chemically etched and untreated surfaces in **Fig. 2 and 3**, a significant improvement in terms of adhered particles is visible, although this improvement is unlikely to be as pronounced in the deeper layers of the material. As shown in **Fig. 3 a**, a higher concentration of particles is already evident in the second layer. This is due to the reduced flow of the etchant into the deeper layers of the structure, despite the experiment being conducted in an ultrasonic bath. The reduction in the thickness of struts and walls within the material is listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Reduction of thickness, d_1 – thickness before etching, d_2 – thickness after etching

sample	d_1 (mm)	d_2 (mm)	reduction of thickness (%)
G1	0.273 ± 0.036	0.148 ± 0.024	45.9
D1	0.272 ± 0.026	0.174 ± 0.027	35.8

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Processing using laser appears to be effective in removing of un-melted particles from the surface layer. Surface melting occurred during laser-treating, which led in the formation of a relatively smooth area and lower surface roughness. Laser processing can also help densify the surface, thereby improving the surface quality, which would lead to better resistance to mechanical damage and material fatigue. However, a limitation of the method is that melting is confined to the region of the laser spot and affects only the upper layer of the printed structure. The laser does not penetrate deeper layers due to the blocking effect of the top layers. **Fig. 3 c, d** shows the laser spot and provides representative images with the designated area enclosed by a dashed line.

Fig. 3: SEM images of a), c) diamond and b), d) gyroid structures modified by a), b) etching and c), d) laser; the area enclosed by dash line shows treated area within the surface of the material

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Typical SEM backscatter electron images and LSCM laser intensity and height maps of the top area of diamond structures are shown in **Fig. 4**. The impact of etching and laser treatment on surface roughness is evident: etching created an irregular surface characterized by rounded valleys, while laser treatment created a more uniform surface. The untreated surface depicted the residual un-melted metallic powder, apparent even on the most exposed top area of the diamond structure, resulting in the S_a value of $(11.8 \pm 1.3) \mu\text{m}$. When the etched samples are considered, rounded valleys were created as the result of the etching process, with no apparent residual powder in the top layer and the S_a value of $(11.1 \pm 2.5) \mu\text{m}$. Although the etched surface possessed a similar roughness to the untreated surface, the weakening of the structure's robustness is observable, as well as some residual powder particles in the deeper layers. The laser-treated structure, when compared to the previous states, possessed the lowest surface roughness of $S_a = (7.3 \pm 0.2) \mu\text{m}$, with a low standard deviation. Typical morphology of the ripple patterns and thermal-induced cracks dominated the newly formed surface already shown in [42], with no residual powder remaining on the top areas and partially melted residual powder particles present in other areas. As for the gyroid structures, the deviations of roughness parameters were rather large, as it is difficult to measure comparable areas between the samples. Yet, the qualitative morphological features were equal to both structures.

Fig. 4: SEM backscatter electron images, LSCM laser intensity and height maps of as-printed, etched and laser-treated samples

3.2 Surface analysis

XRD

The phase composition of the diamond (Fig. 5 a) and gyroid (Fig. 5 b) as-printed and processed structures was analyzed using XRD. As shown in Fig. 5, clear differences can be observed between the as-printed and laser-treated structures. Specifically, the primary difference observed was the presence of TiO (39 wt.%) in the samples within the interaction volume of laser-affected layer. Importantly, this difference was noted regardless of the macrostructure of the as-printed samples. On the other hand, identical phase composition was found in the as-printed and etched samples. This result is expected, particularly due to the absence of thermal effects during etching. More precisely, preferential dissolution of the material during etching may have occurred due to the microstructure and internal stresses introduced by the melting of particles during printing. As a result, uneven dissolution of material may have occurred throughout the volume, but the formation of nonstoichiometric compounds like TiO—formed by the rapid cooling of the melted surface in an oxygen-rich environment—did not take place. Furthermore, differences in crystallite size and microstrain of hexagonal Ti phase were also observed, as indicated by the varying peak widths in Fig. 5. In particular, significantly smaller crystallite size (11 nm) and higher microstrains (0.32%) were recorded in the laser-processed samples compared to the as-printed samples (26 nm, 0.25%) and etched samples (29 nm, 0.22%). Meanwhile, minimal differences between the diamond and gyroid samples were identified, as was the case for phase composition. Overall, all results can be explained by the cooling rate and environmental conditions. The SLM process was conducted under a protective atmosphere, with the printed sample surrounded by powder particles. This setup, in turn, is believed to reduce the cooling rate by gradually increasing the temperature during the process. Conversely, laser processing was performed in air, where oxygen can immediately react with the melted surface. Faster cooling occurred in this case, not only due to heat dissipation

340 into the air but also because the affected volume was significantly smaller. Therefore, a higher cooling rate was achieved
 341 in the laser-treated samples, resulting in smaller crystallites and higher strains in the structure, which ultimately led to the
 342 formation of cracks in the affected layer. Because the results of diffraction showed minimal changes in the phase
 343 composition between etched and as-printed samples, further detailed study was conducted on the alloy whose surface was
 344 treated with a laser. The results were consistently compared with the as-printed state.

345 **Fig. 5:** Diffraction patterns of as-printed, etched and laser-treated structures

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 348 **XPS**

349 XPS measurements were performed using as-printed and laser-treated samples, and the results from these
 350 measurements are shown in **Fig. 6**. The tests revealed that during processing, the thickness of oxides present on the sample
 351 surface increased. This is evident from the Ti and Al spectra, where the peak for Ti⁰ disappeared and the Al⁰ peak was
 352 significantly reduced after processing. In conjunction with the increase in oxygen content (from 23.3 to 30.4 wt.%), the
 353 transformation to oxides due to the increased reactivity of the surface caused by the laser could explain these changes.
 354 Furthermore, the results suggest the presence of TiN and TiC on the surface of both as-printed and laser-treated samples.
 355 However, the overall content of N and C decreased after treatment, from 5.2 wt.% to 3.7 wt.% and from 44.7 wt.% to
 356 31.8 wt.%, respectively. This suggests that the laser may reduce the contamination created on the surface during the
 357 printing process. The most significant change was observed within the V spectra, where the concentration of V increased
 358 from 0 wt.% in the as-printed state to 0.5 wt.% in the laser-treated state. This change could be attributed to the activation
 359 of diffusion, where V atoms are transported toward the surface while Al is transported in the opposite direction. This
 360 phenomenon was described by Lindwall et al. [43]. This could also be a contributing factor in the reduction of the Al⁰
 361 peak intensity. The results indicate that the contamination originated from the fabrication of the sample rather than from
 362 the laser treatment, suggesting no significant negative effects of the process on the surface layer of the samples.

Fig.6: XPS spectra obtained by analysis of as-printed and laser-treated samples

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was primarily conducted on both the as-printed and laser-treated samples. In both cases, strong Raman bands were not observed, with one exception: the spectra of laser-treated samples in the Raman shift range of 200 – 650 cm^{-1} (**Fig. 7 a**). This region exhibited an asymmetrical band with a maximum near 230 cm^{-1} (**Fig. 7 b, c**). These spectra do not correspond to well-defined titanium oxide. A possible interpretation of these bands could be related to a multi-phonon band of nonstoichiometric oxides or oxides lacking a first-order Raman spectrum. Similar observations have been reported in related studies [44, 45]. Additionally, bands corresponding to TiO_2 (~ 430 and 620 cm^{-1} , **Fig. 7 c**) were visible in the laser-treated samples.

Fig. 7: Raman spectra of as-printed and lasered samples together with detailed spectra of lasered a) diamond and b) gyroid structures

3.3 Microstructure

The structure of as-printed samples with a diamond structure (**Fig. 8 a**) and a gyroid structure (**Fig. 8 b**) was composed of a metastable α' phase that forms from the β phase during rapid cooling. In both images, a typical shape of the α' phase is visible, corresponding to needle-like structures. **Fig. 8 c** shows a detail of the structure with a surface modified by laser treatment. Previous results indicated that un-melted particles were removed from the outer layers. As evident, the laser did not affect the structure in the surrounding area. The structure was further composed of a needle-like α' phase. The chemical analysis of the laser-affected area showed an increased content of nitrogen and oxygen. The average chemical composition of the layer was as follows (in wt. %): N: 7.73, O: 27.60, Al: 2.21, Ti: 60.63, V: 1.83. The increased nitrogen and oxygen content was likely due to the atmosphere used during the laser treatment. It can be assumed that the laser-affected area is very fine-grained due to the extremely high cooling rates achieved during this process. Additionally, the thickness of the affected layer was not homogeneous across the surface and varied from 1 to 10 μm . This variation is visible in **Fig. 8 c**, where the thickness can be roughly identified by the cracks within the affected surface. The structure after etching remains practically identical to the as-printed structure. It was also found that the etched structure contained high levels of fluoride. Specifically, these are compounds based on fluoro-complexes [35]. However, a rapidly cooled, fine-grained surface layer does not form; instead, only the previously mentioned thinning of the struts occurs.

Fig. 8: Microstructure of a) D and b) G as-printed samples with presence of α' phase needles; c) a cross-section of DL sample tilted at 45° in SEM showing surface layer cracking

3. 4 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of as-printed and surface treated samples were investigated by compression testing. The results for the diamond and gyroid structures are shown in **Figs. 9 a, b**. **Figs. 9 a, b** demonstrate that the gyroid structure exhibits significantly superior mechanical properties compared to the diamond structure. The gyroid unit cell structure consists of struts and joints, with each node connecting three struts, which predisposes this arrangement to enhanced mechanical properties [3]. In work [46] was found that the primary distinctions lie in the failure mechanisms: the diamond lattice undergoes abrupt failure characterized by the sudden buckling of specific struts within its structure, whereas the gyroid lattice demonstrates a more gradual failure, involving the progressive collapse of its lattice walls. The selected type of printed structure therefore has a significant impact on the resulting mechanical properties. For the printed diamond structure, the yield strength values increased in the following order based on surface treatment: etched < lasered < as-printed (**Fig. 9 a**). The highest ultimate compressive strength was observed in the as-printed sample, while the lowest was found in the etched sample (**Fig. 9 b**). A similar trend can be observed in the compressive strain values. For the printed gyroid structure, the as-printed sample exhibited the best yield strength values, which were measured to be 197 ± 5 MPa. The yield strength for the lasered sample was slightly lower, while significant reductions were observed in the etched samples (**Fig. 9 b**). A similar trend was noted for the ultimate compressive strength values (**Fig. 9 b**). In contrast, elongation was similar for as-printed and lasered samples and the lowest one was observed in the etched sample. Surface treatment by etching significantly deteriorated the mechanical properties of the printed samples (**Fig. 9**). Samples with gyroid printed structures generally exhibited higher values for yield strength, ultimate compressive strength, and elongation compared to those with diamond structures. If surface treatment by etching is to be selected, it would be more suitable to apply this method to samples printed with a gyroid structure. The samples with surfaces modified by etching generally exhibited the worst mechanical properties, which can be attributed to the reduction in strut thickness resulting in the weakening of structure. This is an undesirable side effect that cannot be prevented. Moreover, the such reduction is accompanied by the increasing of pore size leading to the changes in dimension of unit cell [28]. The advantage of

423 etching is primarily a smooth surface [24, 28], meaning potential crack initiators in the form of un-melted particles are
 424 absent, even within the scaffold, as etching acts volumetrically. As is evident, the samples with laser-treated surfaces
 425 performed the best. Surface quality improved, while the mechanical properties did not significantly decrease or were
 426 close to the original as-printed state. Laser treatment resulted in a significant increase in the hardness of the affected area
 427 as was revealed by nanoindentation measurement. Compared to the bulk (5.9 GPa), the surface-affected area exhibited a
 428 hardness of more than 9.5 GPa, representing an increase of over 60%. The elastic modulus of the affected area was also
 429 higher than that of the bulk; however, the difference was less pronounced, with values of 127 GPa and 114 GPa for the
 430 surface area and bulk, respectively. The increase in hardness can be explained by the processes occurring during the laser
 431 treatment. The surface of the material is melted by the laser very quickly, resulting in minimal heat affecting the material
 432 beneath the surface. Additionally, the structure contains pores, and the processing was conducted in air. This suggests
 433 that heat transfer during surface solidification occurs rapidly, leading to high internal stresses and the formation of a fine
 434 microstructure and oxides. These factors directly affect the hardness of the material and explain the observed change in
 435 values.

436 **Fig. 9:** Engineering compressive curves of untreated and treated samples with a) diamond and b) gyroid structures, c)
 437 average values of compressive properties for all tested samples (A value represents the maximal compressive strain value)
 438

439 3.5 Corrosion behavior

441 To assess susceptibility to non-uniform corrosion, all samples were subjected to cyclic polarization in PBS. The
 442 results are presented in **Fig. 10**. The corrosion potentials for most samples reached values around -0.3 V/SSCE, which is
 443 typical for PBS and similar electrolytes [47]. As the potential increased to more noble values, current densities rose,
 444 indicating the reconstruction of the passive layer [48]. Sharp peaks in current density suggest susceptibility to non-uniform
 445 corrosion attacks [20]. However, after these sharp increases, the current density immediately dropped, implying that no
 446 active pits developed in the electrolyte, as supported by lower current density values during reverse polarization.

Fig. 10: Cyclic polarization curves of diamond and gyroid compact samples in PBS

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In comparison to the diamond samples, the gyroid samples exhibit lower non-uniform corrosion resistance with a significantly higher number of sharp peaks which are present in the CP curves. Comparing the current densities, the compact sample exhibits lower current density by order of magnitude which could indicate higher corrosion resistance. However, since the real surface area of the scaffold structures is unknown and only the geometrical area was used to calculate the current densities, it can only be proven the scaffold's real area is considerably higher than the geometrical value. To assess the electrochemical behavior of as-printed and laser-treated samples over an extended period, a physiological saline solution with $9 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ NaCl was chosen due to its high concentration of Cl^- ions equivalent to the concentration in human blood, which attack and dissolve the passive TiO_2 protective layer [49]. Changes in OCP are shown in **Fig. 11 a**. Initially, the OCP slowly increases, indicating moderate growth of the passive layer [50]. Over time, the increase slows, approaching a plateau, which suggests the stabilization of the corrosion process. No significant sharp deviations are observed, indicating the absence of non-uniform corrosion attacks. The OCP values are around -10 mV, consistent with the thermodynamic stability range of TiO_2 for nearly all pH values [51]. The values indicating the passive state align with the findings of Jesus et al. [49]. Differences between individual samples are within 10 mV, which is within the error range of the reference electrode concentration. As is shown in **Fig. 11 b**, as-printed samples show slightly higher overall corrosion resistance, with polarization resistance values around $60 \Omega \cdot \text{m}^2$, compared to laser-treated samples, which have values around $40 \Omega \cdot \text{m}^2$. This may be due to the presence of microcracks on the surface of the laser-treated samples, which impair the function of the protective passive layer (**Fig. 11 e**). This is in good agreement with the confocal measurement. The polarization resistance values for all samples remain relatively stable over time, indicating a stable passive layer on the surface. Fluctuations are more pronounced for as-printed samples, possibly due to localized corrosion attacks and immediate passivation at the sites of partially melted particles on the surface. Cyclic polarization tests conducted immediately after one week of exposure reveal that all samples exhibit numerous sharp peaks in current density (**Fig. 11**). This indicates that chloride ions significantly influence the state of the passive layer, causing non-uniform attacks. Despite this, the cyclic polarization curves show that all materials retain the ability to maintain a compact passive layer on the surface, even at more noble potentials.

Fig. 11: OCP (a), RP (b) and cyclic polarization (d) curves of samples for one-week exposure in physiological solution, c) surface of the laser treated sample

3.6 Cytotoxicity testing

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 479 The metabolic activity of L929 and hFOB 1.19 cells incubated with extracts from both compact TiAl6V4 - as
 480 printed and TiAl6V4 - laser materials was measured. For L929 cells (**Fig 12 a**), there was a statistically significant
 481 difference between the metabolic activity of control cells and cells incubated with TiAl6V4 - as printed extracts ($P \leq$
 482 0.01) as well as TiAl6V4 - laser extracts ($P \leq 0.05$). Nevertheless, the relative metabolic activity was still above the 70%
 483 normative limit relative to the metabolic activity of control cells. Thus, these materials can therefore be considered
 484 cytocompatible according to the standard (ISO 10993-5). No statistically significant difference was observed between the
 485 metabolic activity of cells incubated with TiAl6V4 - as printed and TiAl6V4 - laser extracts. For hFOB 1.19 cells (**Fig.**
 486 **12 b**), there was no statistically significant difference between the metabolic activities of any cell groups (control, those
 487 incubated with TiAl6V4 - laser extracts, or those incubated with TiAl6V4 - as printed extracts). It is well known that
 488 indirect testing (extracts) only reveals chemical toxicity over a short period of time, while the effects of other factors
 489 impacting the cells, such as surface morphology, remain unknown. For this reason, and due to the changes in the material
 490 surface caused by the treatment, direct tests were also performed.

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Fig. 12: Relative metabolic activity of the a) L929 and b) hFOB cell lines incubated in extract of as printed and laser treated TiAl6V4 alloy. Standard deviations were calculated as an average of a minimum of three independent measurements. Statistically significant differences between metabolic activity of Control and TiAl6V4 - as printed (**, $p \leq 0.01$), TiAl6V4 - laser (*, $p \leq 0.05$) are visible in a)

From a qualitative perspective, including cell morphology and interactions with the material, there was no difference between hFOB 1.19 cells growing on TiAl6V4 - as printed and TiAl6V4 - laser materials. The cell was spread out, exhibiting normal morphology and proliferated equally well in both cases (see images after 144 h). However, it was noted that on TiAl6V4 - as printed, the cells were growing only between surface particles, not on them. In the image of the TiAl6V4 - laser material at the 72-h time point (Fig. 13 e), it is interesting to focus on the detail of the lasered structure, where the resulting 'wave-like' pattern appears to be particularly favorable for the cells. This structure is approximately the same size as the cell width, thus creating a suitable environment for cell adhesion and growth. The metabolic activity of hFOB 1.19 cells cultured in the presence of TiAl6V4 - as printed and TiAl6V4 - laser materials was not statistically significantly different. A statistically significant difference was observed between the metabolic activity of control cells and cells cultured in the presence of TiAl6V4 - as printed as well as TiAl6V4 - laser materials. Nevertheless, it was above the normative limit of 70% in all cases, relative to the metabolic activity of control cells. However, it can be inferred that, unlike cells cultured in the presence of TiAl6V4 - as printed material, culturing cells in the presence of TiAl6V4 - laser over a longer time interval leads to leveling of metabolic activities with those of control cells (without the presence of material). The difference in metabolic activities of control cells and cells in the presence of materials may also be due to slight movement of the samples in the wells, which could lead to the death of a small portion of cells growing in direct proximity to the materials.

514
515 **Fig. 13:** Direct cytotoxicity testing of (a), (b), (c) as-printed and (d), (e), (f) laser-treated samples, with (g), (h),
516 (i) corresponding histograms of hFOB 1.19 cell viability evaluated at different time periods of 24, 72, and 144 h
517

518 4. Conclusion

519 The presented study investigated the effect of pulsed laser on the surface state of 3D-printed triply periodic
520 structures in TiAl6V4 alloy. The results were compared with the as-printed condition and the most widely used surface
521 treatment method to date, namely etching. The findings arising from this publication can be summarized into the following
522 points:

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- 524 1) Laser surface treatment successfully removed the adhered un-melted powder particles without affecting the thickness
525 of the supports and walls.
 - 526
 - 527 2) Due to the rapid cooling rate, a new fine-grained layer is formed, and the surface is strengthened by residual stresses.
528 However, cracks were observed in the newly formed layer.
529
 - 530 3) Mechanical property tests revealed that laser surface treatment did not have a negative impact on yield strength,
531 ultimate compressive strength, or ductility. The measured values were close to those obtained for the initial as-printed
532 condition. Additionally, it was found that the gyroid structure exhibits significantly higher mechanical properties
533 compared to the diamond structure. Furthermore, nanointendation tests revealed significant increase (60 %) of hardness
534 value within laser-treated layer. This suggests that laser treatment is superior to etching in this context.
535
 - 536 4) Based on the provided data, all samples exhibited metastable disturbances in the passive layer; however, none showed
537 the development of localized corrosion. The corrosion potential values were within the stability range of titanium oxide.
538 Surface laser treatment resulted in an insignificant decrease in polarization resistance for both types of structures. The
539 applied processing does not have a negative impact on corrosion resistance.
540
 - 541 5) The relative metabolic activity on laser-treated materials significantly exceeded the 70% normative limit relative to the
542 metabolic activity of control cells. Thus, these materials can be considered cytocompatible.

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548 **Data availability**

549 The used data are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14958909>

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